

Operator ID: fb209
Sample ID: PES
Sample Weight: 6.778 mg

PES: PES-1-1.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 2
PES: PES-1-1.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 1
PES: PES-1-2.ds8d
Heat Flow Endo Up (mW) : Step: 1

Funktionspolymere 209

27.03.2019 15:08:23

1) Heat from 20.00°C to 200.00°C at 20.00°C/min